

Proposed Relationship Marketing Strategy for Used Car Dealer

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ABSTRACT: Indonesia has been one of Southeast Asia's largest used car markets. Approximately 2.5-3 million used cars are sold annually. The increased competition in the automotive industry has heightened the emphasis on improving customer relationships. ABC Showroom (pseudonym) is a local used car dealer in Bukittinggi currently facing unsatisfactory sales performance and lacking relationship marketing strategy. The aim of this research is to formulate the relationship marketing strategy for ABC Showroom and find out whether the strategy differs amongst its customer persona.

Internal analysis and external analysis are conducted to formulate the strategy. The internal analysis consists of marketing mix (7P) and STP analysis. The external analysis includes PEST analysis and competitor analysis. A quantitative approach using a survey is carried out to collect information on target market preferences regarding the proposed relationship marketing strategy, specifically personal selling, personalization, and after-sale service. The total of respondents obtained in this research is 240 respondents. The Two-step clustering analysis is conducted to build the customer persona of ABC Showroom. Analysis continued by conducting the Kruskal-Wallis test to find out if the proposed strategies differ amongst customer persona.

Based on the result of the Kruskal-Wallis test, the proposed strategies do not differ amongst customer persona. Findings on internal analysis and external analysis are summarized with a SWOT matrix. Then the TOWS matrix is used to assist the author in formulating the relationship marketing strategy while tailoring it with the survey result. The relationship marketing strategies proposed includes improving salesperson performance by providing target and uniform, providing remarkable test drive experience, providing proactive and caring customer service, providing personalized offers and car products, and providing after-sales services such as warranty, repair, and maintenance service, car ownership transfer and vehicle plate transfer assistance, and car tax payment assistance.

KEYWORDS: After-Sale Service Personal Selling, Personalization, Relationship Marketing, Used Car

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has been one of the largest markets for used cars in Southeast Asia. According to Mendiratta (2021), approximately 2.5-3 million used cars are sold annually [1]. The Indonesian used car market is known to be worth USD 50.77 billion in 2021. Several factors make Indonesia's used car market have its own market share. To begin with, numerous consumers in the country prefer to buy used cars because they are less expensive. Many middle income people have a strong desire to own a car and are not capable of buying a new one. Moreover, many used cars in the market are relatively new, between three to seven years old and in good condition, making them highly feasible possibilities to be explored [2].

Competition within Indonesia used cars market is known to be highly fragmented and competitive with the presence of a large number of unorganized players like local dealerships and individual sellers. There are more than 8,000 dealerships operating in the market and majority of Indonesia sales volume take place through these players [3]. The increased competition in the automotive industry has heightened the emphasis on improving customer relationships [4]. According to Gilbert, as cited in Tuzunkan (2017), there are numerous dealer alternatives and face-to-face communication is considered as a powerful way of communication in the automotive sector, so the necessity to adopt relationship marketing strategies in terms of market conditions is indisputable [5]. Relationship marketing is the process of creating long-term, mutually beneficial relationships between a business and its customers. From the company point of view, relationship marketing is the art of creating special personal ties with its customers. From the customer side, relationship marketing provides an opportunity to communicate their wants and needs and have those needs fulfilled. Companies have to understand customer expectations, provide excellent service and adapt to challenges to survive [6]. Not only companies in the automotive sector must keep their service quality high, they need to personalize their relations with customers as much as possible in order to make a difference in the eyes of customers [5].

ABC Showroom (pseudonym) is a local used car dealer which was established in 2010 in Bukittinggi, West Sumatera. ABC Showroom has been facing low sales performance starting from 2020-2023. Root cause analysis using a fishbone diagram is conducted to find out the root causes that might contribute to the rise of this issue. Root cause analysis of the ABC Showroom business issue can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Showroom ABC sales between 2010-2023 (March)

Several root causes have been successfully identified, including tough competitors, ineffective current marketing strategy, and ineffective salesperson role. Tough competitors with strong financials enable them to provide more variation for the used car they provide. Moreover, some tough competitors have provided other service variations, such as repair and maintenance, that could attract customers more. Furthermore, the lack of a relationship marketing strategy, the dependence on an online platform for promotion, and the unprofessional management of this platform have become other factors contributing to unsatisfactory sales performance. Unsatisfactory sales performance might also happen since there is no target set for the salesperson. In addition, the salesperson in ABC Showroom has been struggling to close the sales due to his unprofessional appearance. It is crucial to formulate marketing strategy for ABC Showroom in order to improve its sales performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Relationship marketing is the process of creating lasting, mutually beneficial relationships between a company and its customers. Relationship marketing, in the perspective of the company, is the art of building special personal ties with its customers. Customers, on the other hand, see relationship marketing as a chance to communicate about their needs and to have those needs met. According to Nwakanma and Jackson (2007), the implementation of relationship marketing can give several benefits, from the company point of view, first, relationship marketing enables the company for achieving both an effective product differentiation and competitive advantage. By putting emphasis on listening to customers, the company can more effectively determine what the customers want and tailor the product to appropriately fit the customer's needs. As the result, the company can be better in differentiating its products and thus gain competitive advantage over those companies which are not as responsive. Secondly, the longer the relationship between the company and its customer, the more profitable the relationship. Since it allows the opportunity for cross selling which increases overall sales volume and potential profit. Moreover, goodwill, which results in word of mouth promotion, assists to lower customer acquisition cost and therefore impacts positively on company profit. Lastly, since relationship marketing encourages the customers to build a long-term relationship with a firm and its product, it can result in a loyal customer [6].

1. Personal Selling

Personal selling is an oral presentation during a conversation with one or more potential buyers to ensure sales [7]. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2016) personal selling is a personal presentation by the company's sales force with the purpose of engaging customers, making sales and building customer relationships [8]. Personal selling activities have become more important as a result of increased competition. Personal selling will help to increase sales and expand markets by identifying

new customers, retaining existing customers, and persuading them to buy more of the company's product by fostering strong customer relationships [9]. A carried out research by Bankole et al. (2021) affirmed that personal selling is able to improve sales efficiency and customer relationship in the service sector [10]. Similar research by Anyadighibe et al. (2014) also shows personal selling succeeds in increasing sales performance and customer retention in the banking industry. In addition, it also enhances customer-firm relationships. Personal selling is a unique way of providing satisfaction to customers, it assists to identify, anticipate, and satisfy customer needs [9]. According to Yudiantoro et al., (2018), customer satisfaction will lead to positive word of mouth. Customers will voluntarily invite their friends or business partner to use the same product or service [11].

2. After-sale service

After-sales service is all types of services provided by a company to the customers after the purchase to ensure customers continue to enjoy trouble-free use of the product throughout its life cycle. After sale service may include maintenance, repair, and warranty [12]. Good after-sales are a vivid manifestation of the modern marketing concept which not only concerns transactions but also cares about customer relations. As automotive products such as vehicles are highly vulnerable to technical and mechanical problems, after-sales service is crucial for attracting new customers and retaining existing customers [13]. In addition, the level of after-sales service is not only important for a customer's decision-making process, but it is also a significant source of revenue for the company. Furthermore according to Russo and Cardinali, as cited in Confente and Russo (2015) after-sales service provides differentiation and positioning in the competitive context [12].

3. Personalization

Personalization is the action of developing and manufacturing in ways that cater to the customer's preferences [14]. According to Imhoff et al. (2001), personalization refers to a company's capacity to recognize and treat its customers as individuals, such as through personal messages, special offers, or other personal transactions. In order to create an individualized customer experience, the company requires to use customer information [15]. Personalized marketing enables companies to gain knowledge about their customers and manage relationships to acquire a competitive advantage [16]. Research conducted by Arora et al. (2021) reveals that 71 percent of customers expect companies to deliver personalized interactions and 76 percent of them get frustrated when it does not happen. In addition, as much as 76 percent of customers said that receiving personalized communications is a crucial factor in prompting their consideration of a brand. Furthermore, 78 percent of customers are more likely to refer colleagues and relatives to companies that personalize [17]. The rising importance of personalization is also evident by the fact that an increase of 5%–15% in revenue as the successful implementation of personalization [18].

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework organize key concepts in the study in order to define the focus and direction of the study. Key concepts are derived from reviewing related topics and findings existing in literature [19]. The key concept constructed in this study is based on the ABC Showroom's business issue and its related root cause. Based on the literature investigation, relationship marketing through personal selling, personalization, and after-sale service are known to improve company sales performance. Thus relationship marketing provided through personal selling, personalization, and after-sale service are proposed as the concepts in this study and expected to help ABC Showroom solve the root cause of the issue and overcome the unsatisfactory sales performance of the ABC Showroom. Conceptual framework of this study can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Research Design

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Figure 3. Research Design

This research is a quantitative research with the objectives to find out relationship marketing strategies that fit ABC Showroom and determine whether the strategies differ amongst ABC Showroom customer persona. A single cross sectional design is used in this research, as the data were collected from participants at a single point of time. To conduct this research, first, business issues exploration and root cause analysis using a fishbone diagram is carried out to find the root causes of the business issue. Then, the research objectives are defined to narrow the focus of the study. Marketing mix (7P), STP analysis, Competitor analysis, and PEST analysis are carried out to analyze the internal and external environment of the company. In this research, the primary data is obtained by doing in-depth interview with ABC Showroom owner and secondary data which include data from journals, reports, books, articles, are gathered to assess the internal and external environment of ABC Showroom. Primary data through a survey is conducted to gather information about target market preferences or opinions towards relationship strategies, specifically personal selling, personalization, and after-sale service. 5 points Likert scale is used, the scores of the options range from 5 = Strongly Agree to 1 = Strongly Disagree respectively. Respondent criteria include men or women aged 28-60 years old, live in West Sumatera, have or have not made transaction with ABC Showroom, and have a minimum income of Rp4,000,000 per month. The research questionnaire of this research can be seen on Table 1. Survey result is analysed statistically using SPSS Statistics Software. Afterwards, the business solution is formulated based on the root cause of the business issue, company internal and external business situations, and survey results with the help of TOWS matrix.

Table 1. Research questionnaire

Variable	Item code	Item	Source
Personal selling	PS 1	I would like to be assisted by salesperson when browsing the cars in the showroom	Firmansyah et al. (2019)
	PS 2	Salesperson who wears appropriate attire or uniform looks trusted and reliable	Ocon and Alvarez (2014)
	PS 3	I would appreciate having a small talk with the salesperson before jumping to cars presentation	Firmansyah et al. (2019)
	PS 4	I would like the salesperson to present or demonstrate the feature and benefit of the cars in detail	Adewale et al. (2019)
	PS 5	I would like to have test drive for the car I am interested in	Lancaster et al. (2019)
	PS 6	I would appreciate if the salesperson contact me after the sale to ask my satisfaction or if there is problem related to the car I had purchased	Adewale et al. (2019)
Personalization	PZ 1	I would like the salesperson personally address communications to me	Arora et al. (2021)
	PZ 2	I would like the showroom to offer me personalized promotions	
	PZ 3	I would like the showroom to offer me relevant product or car accessories	
After-sale service	AS 1	I would like the showroom to provide repair service and maintenance for the car I purchased	Long and Van (2020)
	AS 2	I would like to get warranty for the car I had purchased	Long and Van (2020), Confente and Russo (2015)
	AS 3	I would like the showroom to help me to manage administrative requirements such as transfer of car ownership and vehicle plate number	Confente and Russo (2015)
	AS 4	I would like the showroom to help me to pay the car tax if the area for payment is not reachable area for me	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. PEST Analysis

- **Politic**

Since September 2022, the government has stopped providing incentive for luxury sales tax (PPnBM) on LCGC (Low Cost Green Car) and non-LCGC new cars with engine capacities lower than 1,500 cc. This incentive aimed to increase the sales of new cars which have been impacted due to COVID-19. Based on Regulation of Minister of Finance number 5/PMK010 of 2022, the amount of tax incentive provided was varied, LCGC cars were provided tax incentive up to 100% meanwhile non-LCGC was provided incentive about 50% of PPnBM during certain periods in 2022. The elimination of these incentives could increase demand for used cars since the elimination of incentives will increase the price of new cars.

- **Economics**

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is one of the indicators to evaluate how the economy performs within a country. The increase of GDP reflects economic growth and can be interpreted as a good sign of economic conditions. According to World Bank data (2022), Indonesia's GDP is known to keep strengthening after the GDP falls from \$1.12 trillion to \$1.06 trillion in 2020. In 2021, Indonesia's GDP rise to \$1.19 (12,26% growth) trillion and rise again to \$1.32 trillion (10.9% growth) in 2022. This indicates that Indonesia's economic condition has recovered from COVID-19 [20]. Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) describes the economic condition of a region within a certain period. The higher the region or local productivity, the greater the Gross Regional Domestic Product. GRDP per capita is GRDP divided by the number of population. GRDP per capita depicts the average economic condition of the population [21]. According to data from BPS Provinsi Sumatera, the economy of residents started to recover in 2021 after the drop of GRDP in 2020. There is 3.50% economic growth in 2021 and the growth increase 11.5% in 2022 [22].

- **Social**

Demography is one of the crucial elements in social aspects that need to be assessed. According to BPS (2022), the total population in West Sumatra is estimated to be 5.64 million people. The ABC Showroom is located in Bukittinggi, with a population of 122 thousand people in 2022. All regions in West Sumatra have continued to experience an increase in population in recent years [23]. The rise in population leads to increased demand for transportation, including private vehicles. This condition becomes an opportunity for the ABC Showroom since used cars can be one of the transportation options.

Other social elements that require attention include lifestyle trends and behaviour. According to Asosiasi Penyelenggara Jasa Internet Indonesia (2023), there are 215,626,156 internet users in Indonesia, which accounts for 78.19% of Indonesia's population. West Sumatra is known to have an 80.31% internet penetration rate and become the fifth-highest internet user in Indonesia. Recently, the internet has been utilized not only for accessing information but also for selling and buying media [24]. The internet supports the shift in consumer behaviour, making it easier to conduct business activities digitally [25]. According to Aqsa et al., as cited in Wijaya et al. (2022), the majority of Generation Y and Z want to be able to interact digitally with a relationship-focused approach in the automotive industry [26]. These lifestyle trends and behaviour could become another opportunity for ABC Showroom to optimize its marketing strategy.

- **Technology**

Developments in internet and technology have encouraged the formation of various online platforms and online marketplaces for used cars. Technology has enabled individuals or dealerships to list their cars, provide detailed information, upload pictures, and connect with a wide audience of potential customers. There are several popular online platforms and marketplaces in Indonesia such as OLX Indonesia, Mobil123, Carsome, and Carro.

2. Competitor Analysis

There are two main competitor for ABC Showroom which is Auto B and Auto F, Table 2 will present the analysis of each competitor and the comparison with ABC Showroom.

Table 2. Competitor analysis of ABC Showroom

Indicator		Auto B (pseudonym)	Auto F (pseudonym)	ABC Showroom
Established since		2010	2012	2010
Product and Services	Type of product and service	Car selling and trade-in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Car selling and trade-in Car Salon (body painting; body and machine repair; interior, body, machine detailing; and ceramic coating) 30 days warranty for cars purchased 	Car selling and trade-in
	Type of car sold	LCGC (majority), hatchback, MPV, and SUV. There is no luxury car	LCGC, hatchback, MPV, and SUV	LCGC (majority), Hatchback, MPV (majority), and SUV. There is no luxury car
	Brand	Various Japanese brands such as Toyota, Honda, Daihatsu, Suzuki, Mitsubishi, KIA etc.	Japanese brand (majority) such as Toyota, Honda, Daihatsu, Suzuki, Mitsubishi, KIA etc. and few of Europe brand (Mercedes, Opel, BMW)	Japanese brand (majority) such as Toyota, Honda, Daihatsu, Suzuki, Mitsubishi, KIA etc. and few of Europe brand (VW)
	Number of inventory	40-45 cars	35-40 cars	25-30 cars
Price		Price varies, depending on the car type, brand and year.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Car: varied, depends on type of car, brand and car year Car salon: varied, depends on the service (For instance: Interior detailing: Rp400,000) 	Price varies, depending on the car type, brand and year. ABC Showroom has a set profit margin which amounts to 7-10% to stay competitive. In addition, ABC Showroom provide discount Rp 1,000,000-Rp.2,000,000
Place and Physical evidence		Dealer is located in a quite strategic area (right beside the main road but with less crowded people)	Dealer is located in a quite strategic area (right beside the main road but with less crowded people)	Dealer is located in a strategic location (right beside the main road and crowded with people due to being located in a business district area)
Marketing Channel (Promotion)		-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media: Instagram and Facebook Online marketplace (momobil.id) Banner 	Online marketplace (olx.co.id)
Process		Customer visit the dealer → look around and assistance by salesperson → test drive → transaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer visit the dealer → look around and assistance by salesperson → test drive transaction → after-sale service (30 days warranty) Customer find or visit Auto F's Instagram/Facebook /momobil.id → visit the dealer to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Customer visit the dealer → look around and assistance by salesperson → test drive → transaction Customer find ABC Showroom advertisement on olx.co.id → discussion

		check the car and assistance by salesperson → test drive → transaction → after-sale service (30 days warranty)	through Olx chatting feature → visit the dealer to check the car → assistance by salesperson → test drive → transaction
People	Customer directly served by the owner and 3 salesperson	Customer directly served by the owner and 3 salesperson	Customer directly served by ABC Showroom owner or a salesperson
Strength	Large variation of inventory due to strong financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large variation of inventory due to strong financial • Provides additional service (car salon) • Quite good online presence • Provide warranty as assurance for customer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic location • Competitive price • Rigorous inspection
Weakness	Currently lacks of marketing effort. Auto B only wait for customer to visit the showroom	Less decent area for further discussing with customer	Only relies on an online marketplace for marketing effort

According to table 2 above, there are several key findings which describe the competitive frame between ABC Showroom and its main competitor:

- a. In terms of additional services provided, ABC Showroom is far behind Auto F. Additional services can help to attract potential customers and introduce the Auto F brand. People who initially only use additional services provided by Auto F have the opportunity to be potential customers since they are already familiar with and have trust towards Auto F. Satisfied customers can also provide positive word of mouth (WOM), which might help Auto F to acquire more potential customers.
- b. In terms of assurance towards customers, the warranty provided by Auto F enables it to become competitive. Warranty can ease customer concerns towards the quality of the used car they have purchased. On the other hand, ABC Showroom does not provide such assurance, when in fact, ABC Showroom is known to have strict inspection before deciding to put the cars in the showroom to ensure all the vehicles it provides have good quality. Careful inspection is conducted to avoid a car with a history of traffic accidents, submerged in flood, and used as a shuttle. Only the car with minor or non-fatal damage on its outer body is accepted. To conclude, ABC Showroom must provide assurance and show its commitment to delivering high-quality cars through warranty.
- c. In terms of product inventory, ABC Showroom is far behind both competitors. According to the ABC Showroom owner, the number of inventory can become an advantage since customers love to visit big dealers with a large variety of cars to be chosen.
- d. In terms of the marketing channel, ABC Showroom is left behind by one of its main competitors. Auto F has more marketing channels and quite a good online presence by promoting its product in both marketplace and social media. Auto F has 343 followers on Instagram and 100 followers on Facebook.
- e. In terms of the place, ABC Showroom has the most strategic location compared to its main competitors. ABC Showroom is located in a business district crowded with people and right beside the main road, which gives it good visibility.

3. Marketing Mix (7P)

a. Product

ABC Showroom has been providing various types of cars from various brands since 2010. Recently, ABC Showroom has provided 25-30 vehicles as its inventory. They provide MPV, Hatchback, SUV, and LCGC from various Japanese brands, with most cars aged within 5-15 years. ABC Showroom has prioritised providing MPV and LCGC cars from Japanese brands such as Toyota, Honda, and Daihatsu since the demand for these products is relatively high. European brands are rare to be found in this showroom. But they have been providing some variants of VW.

b. Price

The price of cars in ABC Showroom usually ranges from Rp55.000.000-Rp.475.000.000. ABC Showroom determines its product price based on the car's cost of goods sold (COGS). ABC showrooms usually set a profit margin of 7-10% based on the car type, brand, and demand to provide a competitive price. They are pretty flexible when customers try to bargain the car price. ABC Showroom can give a discount maximum of Rp1,500,000-2,000,000 depends on the car type.

c. Promotion

ABC Showroom only depends on a marketplace, namely olx.co.id, which ABC Showroom owner directly handles. The owner will list the cars, provide information, and interact with potential customers digitally through this marketplace. ABC Showroom used to do promotions using newspapers and billboards from 2013-2015, but the owner said that it was ineffective and did not improve their sales. Due to utilizing the Olx in September 2017 as the marketing effort, many customers outside of the town visited the showroom, resulting in a spike in sales in 2018 and 2019. Even so, this marketing channel did not significantly impact ABC Showroom like it used to do. ABC Showroom is still struggling with its sales performance even though ABC Showroom always utilizes this channel. Another problem which also needs to be addressed related to this marketing channel is the slow response of ABC Showroom owner in replying to messages from potential customers and the unprofessional chat manner. Furthermore, ABC Showroom needs to optimize the advertisement with detailed descriptions of the car's characteristics and condition. The advertisements only consist of "Excellent condition, entirely original, well maintained" and the address of the ABC Showroom dealer. According to Kim and Lennon (2008), detailed verbal descriptions of a product are crucial since they positively influence consumer purchase decisions and the Internet shopping experience. Providing more detailed information related to the car will assist the customers in evaluating the products and yielding a more positive attitude which can lead to a purchase decision [27].

d. Place

ABC Showroom is located on the main road, which makes it easy to be found and has high visibility. ABC Showroom is located in the business district crowded with people, thus making its place strategic.

e. People

The owner of ABC Showroom employs 4 people to run the business, which consist of a secretary, a salesperson, a mechanic, and a janitor. The salesperson together with the owner are the one who directly serve the customer in the showroom and leads them to sales. There is no marketing division or specific marketing staff that plans and handles the marketing effort of ABC Showroom. Plans and decisions related to marketing come from the owner of ABC Showroom. The past marketing efforts are mostly conducted by intuition and trial and error from the ABC Showroom owner.

f. Process

Figure 4. Purchase Process of ABC Showroom

As we see in Figure 4, the process starts with a potential customer who finds the ABC Showroom on olx.co.id and contacts the showroom through the olx.co.id message feature to ask for more information about the car they are interested in. The ABC Showroom owner will provide the information they need and will try to direct them to visit the showroom to see the car. Both potential customers from olx.co.id and potential customers that directly visit the showroom will be served by the ABC Showroom owner or salesperson. The salesperson or ABC Showroom owner will deliver a presentation (explaining car attributes and benefits) and demonstration of the car. Some demonstrations include encouraging customers to have a test drive. After that, the ABC Showroom owner or salesperson will have the discussion and negotiation of the car that the customers are interested in. The salesperson is unable to handle customer objections regarding the price negotiation. Customers prefer to continue negotiating the car with the ABC Showroom owner. Some customers also prefer to negotiate the price directly with the ABC Showroom owner. This occurrence might be due to the unprofessional appearance of the salesperson. The unprofessional appearance affects customer trust towards the salesperson. According to Grewal, et al., as cited in Ghanadiof et al.. (2021), salesperson appearance is one of the factors influencing customer trust [28]. Trust is an essential factor in the customer-salesperson relationship and affects the ability of a salesperson to influence a customer [29]. Thus it is crucial to change the appearance of the salesperson. In addition, when the customer asks for the ABC Showroom owner to negotiate the price, the salesperson would just direct the customer to the ABC Showroom owner. This action might be due to the absence of a target for the salesperson. ABC Showroom does not require the salesperson to close the sales with a certain target, and the salesperson will always be provided with a bonus regardless of who closes the sales. After discussing and negotiating the cars, the transaction will occur. After the transaction, the ABC Showroom owner and the salesperson do not follow up with the customers regarding the problems they might have faced and their satisfaction. ABC Showroom owner only provided the customers with his number and asked them to contact him when there was a problem with the purchased car. This after-sales activity needs to be improved as Fabian, as cited in Firmansyah et al. (2018), argues that follow-up is the most critical step to building long-term seller-customer relationships. To effectively build relationships, the seller has to ensure customer satisfaction by following through with value-added services after the sale [7]. To conclude the process, ABC Showroom needs to improve the handling objections process and the after-sales activities.

g. Physical Evidence

Physical environment of the showroom also posed the tangible factor that cues the quality of experience that ABC Showroom provides. ABC showroom provides clean surroundings and decent office for discussing or having conversation with the customers.

4. STP Analysis

a. Segmenting

Table 3. Segmentation of ABC Showroom

Segmentation type		Description
Geographic	Country	Indonesia
	Region	West Sumatera
	Rural - Urban Area	Rural and urban area
	Gender	Male and Female
	Age	28- 60 years old

Demographic	Occupation	Entrepreneurs, Employees, civil servant
	Social class	Middle income to upper income
	Education background	Educated
	Marital status	Married or single
Psychographic	Active, value shopper	
Behavioral	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Browsing through internet or marketplace to compare prices • Knowledgeable or not knowledgeable about used car • Going to one dealer after another in order to find good quality used car with the best deal • Buying based on family or friends recommendation 	

b. Targeting

The target market of ABC Showroom shared similar characteristics in terms of functional and monetary value. This target market includes budget conscious consumers and do not want to compromise the quality and the safety of the used car. Detail of ABC Showroom target include: Age 28-60 years old, have an income minimum Rp4,000,000 per month, digital savvy or not, parents who is looking for family transportation, an employee who is looking for company operations, and young individuals who recently obtained a driver's license and are looking for affordable options.

c. Positioning

Positioning serves as an idea and what positions a firm wants to occupy in the market. ABC Showroom positioned itself as the used dealer providing high-quality used cars at competitive prices. By providing rigorous inspections towards the used car, ABC Showroom ensures to provide high-quality used cars that can be afforded by customers who have budget limitations.

5. SWOT Analysis

The results from previous internal and external analysis of ABC Showroom are further classified to strength, weakness, opportunities, and threat and organized using the SWOT matrix in Table below.

Table 4. SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
S1.Strategic location S2. Rigorous inspection to ensure the quality of used car S3. Provide competitive price	W1. There is no target and lack of professional appearance of salesperson W2. Passive role of salesperson in after-sale stage of personal selling W3 Limited product and service to improve customer relationship W4. Lack of personalization W5. Only depend on an online marketplace for marketing effort W6. The marketplace do not handled professionally (slow response, lack of personalization in communication, unprofessional chat)

Opportunities	Threats
O1. Improvement of economic condition that drives customer purchase power O2. High rate of internet penetration	T1. Competitor with strong financial T2. Bigger competitor with various type of services

6. Validity and reliability result

In this study, the validity test using the Pearson correlation product moment test is carried out to determine the validity of the instruments used. This test determines the correlation between item's scores and total scores on each variable. Item is considered valid if its r-count exceeds the value of the r-table. if the r-count is less than the value of the r-table, thus the item is considered not valid. Validity test result can be seen on Table 5.

Table 5. Questionnaire validity result

Variable	Question code	r count value	r table value (Significant at 95%)	Description
Personal selling	PS1	0.456	0.312	Valid
	PS2	0.833	0.312	Valid
	PS3	0.582	0.312	Valid
	PS4	0.916	0.312	Valid
	PS5	0.835	0.312	Valid
	PS6	0.801	0.312	Valid
Personalization	PZ1	0.553	0.312	Valid
	PZ2	0.661	0.312	Valid
	PZ3	0.607	0.312	Valid
After-sales service	AS1	0.847	0.312	Valid
	AS2	0.600	0.312	Valid
	AS3	0.656	0.312	Valid
	AS4	0.550	0.312	Valid

According to Table 5 above, all the items of the questionnaire are valid since the Pearson correlation coefficient (r-count) is greater than the r-table critical value. After testing the validity of the questionnaire, the reliability test is conducted using Cronbach's Alpha test to find out the variable consistency. The reliability test result can be seen in Table 6. According to Table 6, all variables in this research are known to be reliable since the Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.6.

Table 6. Reliability test result of the questionnaire

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha value	Description
Personal selling	0.786	Reliable
Personalization	0.784	Reliable
After-sale service	0.828	Reliable

7. Cluster Analysis

Cluster analysis using Two-step cluster analysis was conducted to develop the customer persona of ABC Showroom. In this research, the number of clusters or customer persona developed is 3 personas. Clustering of respondents was generated based on respondents's age, gender, education, income, and occupation. According to Looma and Lawan, as cited in Puska (2018), demographic factors, such as age, gender, occupation, education and income, are key variables that influence consumer behavior. For instance, females tend to consult more to salesperson, look for more alternatives, and make decisions to purchase at home. On the other hand, male respondents are more satisfied with their own purchase decision [30]. Based on the Two-step clustering result, Persona 1 (Cluster 1) is the persona with the largest size which amounts to 55% of respondents. Persona 2 (Cluster 2) is the second largest persona consisting of 30% of respondents. Persona 3 (Cluster 3) is the persona with the smallest size which consists of 15% of respondents. Detailed characteristics of each cluster persona will be presented in Table 7. According to Table 7, Persona 1 is an early 40's male who is a high school graduate and works as an entrepreneur. The income that he generates is Rp4,000,000- Rp5,000,000. Persona 2 is an early 40's male who is a bachelor graduate and works as an entrepreneur. The income that he generates is Rp 4,000,000- Rp5,000,000. Persona 3 is a late 40's female who is a bachelor graduate and works as a civil servant. The income that she generates is Rp5,000,000- Rp 10,000,000. Further persona development is done by interviewing several samples of respondents that belong to each persona cluster. Data collected such as preferred media for searching used cars, preference of brand and type of used cars, purchasing purpose, factors considered when purchasing a used car, preferred payment method, pain points, and knowledge about used cars.

Table 7. Cluster Characteristics

Indicator	Persona 1	Persona 2	Persona 3
Gender	Male	Male	Female
Education	High school	Bachelor	Bachelor
Occupation	Entrepreneur	Entrepreneur	Civil servant
Income	Rp4,000,000- Rp5,000,000	Rp4,000,000- Rp5,000,000	Rp5,000,000- Rp10,000,000
Average age	41.42	40.51	47.03

The first customer persona of ABC Showroom is a man in his late millennial called Bambang. He is in his early 40' and currently working as an entrepreneur. He has a middle income and has moderate knowledge about used cars. He is social media savvy and he explores used cars on online platforms to compare several alternatives. He prefers Low Cost Green Car (LCGC) and Multi-purpose vehicle (MPV) with a budget of < Rp100,000,000. His considerations for buying a used car are competitive price and good condition. He prefers cash and credit as payment methods. His brand preferences are Suzuki and Toyota. His fears of buying a used car are afraid to get an unfair value of the car and a car buying process that is not transparent. The second customer persona is a father. His name is Budi. He is in his early 40' and currently working as an entrepreneur. He has a middle income and has low knowledge about used cars. He is social media savvy and he explores used cars on online platforms to compare several alternatives. He prefers Low Cost Green Car (LCGC) and multi-purpose vehicles (MPV) with a budget of Rp,100,000,000 - Rp120,000,000. His considerations for buying a used car are

competitive price, good condition, and reputable seller. He prefers credit as payment methods. His brand preferences are Toyota and Daihatsu. His fears of buying a used car are afraid to get an unfair value of the car and bad quality used car. The third customer persona is a career woman. She is Wati and in her late 40' and currently working as a civil servant. She has a middle to upper income and has low knowledge about used cars. She is old school thus she goes to used car dealers to explore the used car. She prefers multi-purpose vehicles (MPV) and Sport Utility vehicles (SUV) with a budget of Rp150,000,000 - Rp200,000,000. Her considerations for buying a used car are easy car buying process, competitive price, good car condition. She prefers debit and cash as payment methods. Her brand preferences are Toyota and Honda. Her fear is that it is hard to find a car that suits her preferences and hard to find time for purchasing the car. Preferences or opinions of each customer persona towards personal selling, personalization, and after-sales service can be seen in Table 8 below.

Table 8. Customer persona opinions towards personal selling, personalization, after-sale service

Variable	Persona	Mean	Median	Standard deviation
Personal selling	1	4.49242	4.66667	.54829
	2	4.38889	4.50000	.62985
	3	4.45833	4.58333	.55259
Personalization	1	4.31566	4.33333	.70056
	2	4.20370	4.33333	.73703
	3	4.31481	4.33333	.56873
After-sale service	1	4.60606	4.75000	.50486
	2	4.54861	4.87500	.62467
	3	4.55556	4.50000	.46718

8. Kruskal-Wallis test

Kruskal-Wallis test is conducted to find out whether the relationship marketing strategies trough personal selling, personalization, and after-sale service differ among customer persona. Kruskal-Wallis test is conducted since the data in this research is not normally distributed (Based on Normality test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov). The result of the Kruskal-Wallis test is presented in Table 9. As can be seen below, the p-value of all the research variables is greater than 0.05, thus it can be concluded that the personal selling, personalization, and after-sales service do not differ among customer persona. All of customer persona demands for personal selling, personalization, and after-sales service.

Table 9. Kruskal Wallis result

Variables	P-value	Description
Personal Selling	0.723	Not significantly different
Personalization	0.567	Not significantly different
After sale service	0.764	Not significantly different

9. Proposed Business solutions

The TOWS matrix is used to assist the author in formulating the relationship marketing strategy while tailoring it with the survey result. TOWS matrix can be seen in Table 10 below.

TOWS Matrix	Strengths	Weaknesses
	S1.Strategic location S2. Rigours inspection to ensure the quality of used car	W1. There is no target and lack of professional appearance of salesperson

	S3. Provide competitive price	W2. Passive role of salesperson in after-sale stage of personal selling W3 Limited product and service to improve customer relationship W4. Lack of personalization W5. Only depend on an online marketplace for marketing effort W6. The marketplace do not handled professionally (slow response, lack of personalization in communication, unprofessional chat)
Opportunities	S-O Strategies	W-O Strategies
O1. Improvement of economic condition that drives customer purchase power O2. High rate of internet penetration	S2,O1-O2 Provide remarkable test drive experience	W1O1 Improve salesperson performance by providing target and uniform W3-W4,O1 Provide personalized offer and car product or accessories W5O2 Utilize more online platform and social media W5,O1-O2 Optimize current online platform (olx.co.id) W6,O1-O2 Hire an admin to handle online platform
Threats	T-S Strategies	W-T Strategies
T1. Competitor with strong financial T2. Bigger competitor with various type of service	S1-S3,T1-T2 Provide eye catching and informative banner in front of ABC Showroom	W2,T1-T2 Encourage salesperson to be proactive and caring "customer service" W3,T1-T2 Provide after-sales service

• **Personal Selling**

Personal selling is one of crucial technique for building customer relationships. According to the survey, the target customer would like to be assisted by a salesperson while browsing the showroom. They also want the salesperson to provide detailed information related to the car's features and benefits when the salesperson does a presentation or demonstration. In addition, there are several aspects that ABC Showroom needs to improve regarding its personal selling process, such as:

(W1,O1) Improve salesperson performance by providing target and uniform

ABC Showroom owner needs to provide sales targets to drive the salesperson's motivation, thus improving salesperson performance. Current regulations related to incentives or bonuses are also recommended to be revised (the salesperson has always been provided with a bonus if there is a sale or successful transaction in the showroom, regardless of who closes the sales). Provide realistic targets with sufficient incentive. For example, the salesperson must close 10 sales a month and be provided with a 5% incentive rate each time he successfully closes the sales. In addition, the salesperson also needs to be equipped with proper attire, like a uniform, to improve customer perception and trust towards the salesperson. According to the survey, the target market thinks a salesperson with formal attire or uniform looks trustworthy and reliable. The colour uniforms need to resonate with the ABC Showroom brand. In addition, add the ABC Showroom logo on a conspicuous spot. This logo placement helps create brand awareness and build a professional business image of ABC Showroom.

(S2,O1-O2) Provide remarkable test drive experience

Test drive is an example of product demonstration conducted or assisted by salesperson. According to the survey result, target market would like to have test drive for the car they are interested in. ABC Showroom need to provide remarkable test drive experience for them. There are several ways that ABC Showroom can do. First, ABC Showroom needs to create a selection of different driving routes to show the car's capabilities. Customers can choose the routes that ABC Showroom suggests. Second, provide an extended test drive period. Allow customers to spend more time with the cars. It will give them a better feel for the car's performance, comfort, and features. This extended experience can build a stronger connection and provide a more comprehensive evaluation towards the car.

(W2,T1-T2) Provide proactive and caring customer service

According to the survey result, the target market would appreciate it if the salesperson could follow up on purchase satisfaction and any issues related to the purchase. ABC Showroom needs to empower the salesperson to be proactive and caring "customer service" in the after-sales activities stage. After the sales happen, the salesperson must reach out to customers regarding their satisfaction towards the car they purchase and ask if there is any problem regarding the car. If the customer has a problem, the salesperson must offer help. Equipped the salesperson with chat etiquette to keep a professional manner. Some chatting etiquette includes responding quickly, using proper grammar and spelling, avoiding slang, and being empathetic. In addition, before ending the conversation, the salesperson should ensure that any issue is fully addressed. After that, the salesperson could ask for feedback or encourage customers to provide online reviews if they are satisfied with the purchase or the service. Ultimately, thanking them and wishing customers a good day or providing a similarly friendly closing is also suggested.

- **Personalization**

(W3-W4,O1) Provide personalized offer and car product

According to the survey result, the target market wants to be offered personalized offers and car products or accessories. ABC Showroom must provide personalized offers and products that might interest customers. ABC Showroom must know the customers' needs and preferences to give and tailor such personalization. Personal selling can be utilized as a quick tool to identify customers' needs and preferences. Personal selling enables the salesperson to get the picture of what kind of offer and product may be needed based on certain relevant information such as occupation, age, daily activities, etc. Offers and car product personalization can also be tailored based on the type of car a customer buys, the type of payment, and the motive or objective behind the purchase. In this research there are three persona of ABC Showroom customers.

The first customer persona is Bambang, he is 41 years old and social media savvy, creative, and active person. He prefers cash and credit as payment methods. Based on this information, some personalized products that might interest Bambang are a mobile phone mount to keep his phone safe, a phone charger port, and a Bluetooth car adapter. Since Bambang is an active person, ABC Showroom can also offer seat covers that prevent wear and tear, spills, and stains. Personalized offers that can be provided such as a discount for car maintenance, car wash voucher, and discount car insurance for the credit card payment method.

The second customer persona is Budi. He is a 41 years old father. He is social media savvy, family man, and a hard worker person. He prefers credit as payment methods. His purpose of purchasing a used car is for family transportation. Based on this information several personalized products that ABC Showroom can offer such as car phone holder, a phone charger port, and a Bluetooth car adapter because Budi is social media savvy. Since the purpose of this car is for family transportation, ABC Showroom can offer a car organizer to keep the kids and family essentials ready in the car to avoid mess, backseat entertainment system that keeps children entertained on long drives, mini vacuum portable, toddler seat, and car seat protectors to avoid stains and spills. Personalized offer like an all-risk insurance discount can be provided for Budi especially if he is considering taking quite a long instalment payment and living in the rural area. Another personalized offer that can be provided include a car wash voucher and voucher for free car maintenance service.

The third customer persona is a career woman. Her name is Wati. She is 47 years old and currently working as a civil servant. She has a middle to upper income and has low knowledge about used cars. She is old school, active and a hard

worker. Since Wati is an active person, to keep the car clean ABC Showroom can offer a mini vacuum cleaner, a car organizer, and durable and easy-to-clean floor mats that can protect the car flooring from dirt, mud, and spills. A mini diffuser can also be offered for Wati to make her trip to the office more enjoyable.

A partnership with several car accessories shops can be done to satisfy customers' needs and preferences regarding car products and offerings. ABC Showroom is suggested to provide customers with a product catalogue in the showroom to enable them to see the product or car accessories.

(W6,O2) Hire an admin to handle online platform

ABC Showroom owner only has a little time to handle the online platform, resulting in slow responses to potential customer messages. It could lead to a loss of potential sales. In addition, it creates a negative image or impression of ABC Showroom in the customer's eyes. The lack of past personalization in the communication and less professional chatting could also have imposed the ABC Showroom toward this image. According to the survey, the target market wants to be addressed personally when communicating with them. To address all these issues, especially with the slow response, ABC Showroom needs to hire a deft admin with good written communication skills. In addition, the hired admin must be equipped with product knowledge to satisfy customer interest.

- **After-sale service**

(W3,T1-T2) Provide after-sale service

ABC Showroom needs to adopt several types of after-sales services to attract potential customers and build long-term relationships with current customers. First is warranty; the warranty is one of the crucial elements in after-sales service that can assure customers. It will help relieve customer concerns regarding the car quality they purchased. Providing a warranty will help to ease the customer's concern. Based on the survey findings, target market demand for warranty for the car they bought. ABC Showroom can provide a 30 days machine warranty to assure the quality of the used car it sells. This warranty will cover any breakdown related to the machine and give such responsibility as free repair for the machine. Second, Provide repair and maintenance service. According to the survey result, the target market would like ABC Showroom to be equipped with repair and maintenance services. Providing repair and maintenance services can also help ABC Showroom gain competitive conditions since one of its main competitors provides the same service. Several examples of repair services that ABC Showroom need to provide are machine repair and detailing, body painting and detailing, and interior detailing. In addition, examples of car maintenance that ABC Showroom can provide are oil changes, brake canvas and fluid replacement, AC and machine air filter replacement, spark plug replacement, and car battery replacement. Third, Provide car ownership transfer and vehicle plate transfer assistance. The procedure for transferring car ownership or vehicle plate is usually tiring since it requires a customer to follow several processes with long queues. Based on the survey finding, the target market demands this type of after-sale service. Lastly, provide car tax payment assistance. According to the survey, customers want car tax payment assistance when the payment location is hard to reach. ABC Showroom needs to provide car tax payment assistance to ease customer concerns about their difficulty to pay the car tax.

- **Supporting strategies**

(W5, O1-O2) Optimize current online platform (olx.co.id)

ABC Showroom needs to optimize the advertisement in the olx.co.id by providing more detailed conditions and characteristics of the car. Instead of providing less assurance and subjective descriptions such as "Excellent condition, entirely original, well maintained," ABC Showroom can provide a summary of car inspection results in the advertisement description. For instance, "Car clutch operates smoothly" or "well maintained machine with no rust and no loud noise". ABC Showroom also needs to provide a detailed description of the car, such as the km of the car, tax payment period, and detailed car specifications. In addition, ABC Showroom can provide information related to the after-sale service to attract customers more.

(W5, O1-O2) Utilize more online marketplace and social media

ABC Showroom owner only relies on one online marketplace which is olx.co.id as its marketing effort. As the internet penetration rate in West Sumatera is high, ABC Showroom needs to expand its digital presence by listing its car on

other online marketplaces to reach more potential customers. In this research, persona 1 and 2 are media social savvy, thus it is crucial for ABC Showroom to improve its online presence through marketplace and social media. Some online marketplaces include Mobil123, Carro, and Carsome. Facebook marketplace is a free marketplace that can also be utilized. In addition, to strengthen the digital presence of ABC Showroom, ABC Showroom can create social media accounts such as Facebook and Instagram.

(S1-S4,O1) Provide eye catching and informative banner in front of ABC Showroom

ABC Showroom is located in the business district area. ABC Showroom can utilize its strategic location to attract customers and improve brand awareness using a banner that is placed in front of the Showroom. The banner not only has to be eye-catching enough to attract attention but also has to be informative related to the product and service provided by the Showroom. In addition, the banner's colour needs to represent ABC Showroom and provide its unique selling proposition.

CONCLUSION

There are three components within relationship marketing strategy that can be implemented for all of customer persona of ABC Showroom which includes personal selling, personalization, and after-sales service. In personal selling, companies may want to provide targets for salesperson, provide employees with proper sales attire to improve the salesperson's performance and gain more trust to the customer; Provide remarkable test drive experience; and provide proactive and caring "customer service. Moreover, in order to maximize personalization, provide personalized offer and car product. Lastly, providing after-sale services could be done by offering 30-days machine warranty, repair and maintenance service, car ownership transfer and vehicle plate transfer assistance, and car tax payment assistance. Several supporting strategies that need to be done include optimizing the current online marketplace, utilizing more online marketplace and social media, and providing eye-catching and informative banners. All of this strategy is expected to increase sales of ABC Showroom.

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